

3 Poems by Dr Sanjukta Dasgupta

DYSTOPIA

Here lies the cactus land
Ashes carpet the dry earth
Sighs rise like siren songs
Here there are no tears
Here there are no fears
Here there is no water
Here rivers are suicidal
Subterranean stock still

Will the cacti flower someday
Like hope out of hopelessness

The steel grey sky above
Inscrutable as invisible God

Sanjukta Dasgupta
July 27, 2025

Neverland

Simon Bolivar dreamt:

I wish I could reach Neverland
I wish my friend was Peter Pan
I wish I could hear Tinker Bell

In Neverland there are no monstrous humans
Greedy gluttons
Salivating for others' treasures
Killing stealing bullying
Ravaging all corners
Of the helpless earth

When will God break the silence
As the oil of another
Is siphoned off by a brute
When a leader of an oil-rich country
Is kidnapped to enable loot

As Simon Bolivar raised his voice
Peter Pan cried his
Forever young heart out
Wondering what magic

Can make the Satanic earth
Change into a greed-free
Godly Neverland.

Sanjukta Dasgupta
January 4th 2025

I don't love you anymore

*“forgot that you existed
And I thought that it would kill me, but it didn't
And it was so nice
So peaceful and quiet
I forgot that you existed
I did, I did, I did
It isn't hate, it's just indifference
Oh yeah”*
Taylor Swift

**In his inimitable baritone
When the Calcutta boy
Englebert Humperdink
Heart wrenchingly sang
'Release Me'
Was it about cancel culture
Of the new millennium**

**I want to believe
I don't love you anymore
But I fall in love with you
Head over heels even more
Any more is not no more
Any more is ever more**

**As the lover knows
As George Michael did
The love of last Christmas
Ended as soon as it began
The search for someone special
Lasts lifelong, evermore**

**Unlike Taylor Swift's
Liberating indifference
I remain locked to you
Though I don't love you anymore**

**The key is lost my love
I wish I did not
Love you anymore**

**This earth where I was born
This land of my many loves
My lovely parents and friends
My countless chameleon lovers
Butterflies and caterpillars
I am the lover Krishna incarnate
How can I not love you all anymore!**

Sanjukta Dasgupta
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<https://lucywritersplatform.com/2022/05/12/sanjukta-dasgupta-in-conversation-with-basudhara-roy/>
<https://countercurrents.org/2022/07/book-review-it-begins-at-home-and-other-short-stories/mposure>
of Amita Ray's seventeen stories in the „Twilight Raga“ will delight readers as they are both reader-friendly and deeply meaningful. The publisher however needs to pay meticulous attention to copy-editing